

RISE OF FRENCH FAR-RIGHT: ITS IMPACT ON IMMIGRATION POLICY

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Abstract

The far-right has generally remained outside of policymaking, but it has been a factor in policy development in European countries. The far-right parties have been co-opted by the mainstream parties in the past and present. However, there has always been a lack of understanding of this process. This co-option is a strategy by the mainstream parties to incorporate the rival group's political proposal into the decision-making process. As this co-option alters the policy, it also changes the engagement of political parties among themselves and electoral divisions.

This paper discusses the rise of the National Front (now the National Rally) in France and its impact on French immigration policy. FN has been the leading force in France's political debate on immigration since the start of the 1980s. The rise of the FN has threatened the democratic institutions in place, and her politics wish to curtail the liberties of immigrants in France. She influenced the country's debate on immigration, integration, Islam, and the response to the refugee crisis in Europe. This paper will analyse two issues: What impact does NR have on inter-party competition and immigration policy? And how does NR's politics mould the public's attitude towards this social phenomenon?

Keywords: Immigration, National Front, Far-Right, France, Foreign Policy

Introduction

In Western liberal democracies, extreme right-wing populist groups are becoming more and more popular in modern-day Europe. Europeans' mistrust of the present governments and political elites has been exacerbated by migration, financial crises, and further globalisation

(Rydgren, 2017, p. 485). Since the turn of the century, most European nations have experienced a significant increase in the population's immigrant proportion. Parties that have steadily gained electoral support since the 1980s include the FPÖ (Austria), the Danish People's Party (Denmark), and Lijst Pim Fortuyn (Netherlands), among many others (Rydgren, 2017, p. 485). While the rapid rise in the immigrant share of the population has presented significant policy challenges for European countries, including assimilation, education, and employment, among others, the rise of far-right political parties has been seen by many observers as posing a more fundamental problem. As opponents of expanding globalisation and immigration from the Middle East and Africa, far-right parties gained popularity in Western European party systems throughout the 1980s and 1990s (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 242). In addition to being fierce opponents of neo-liberalism, immigration, and European integration (Euroscepticism), they challenged established parties as a new anti-establishment group (Zaslove, 2008, p. 169).

The fundamental goal of a far-right party is to uphold the nation's traits, customs, and values. When searching for stories about the distant past, far-right parties turn to ancient history (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 243). Restoring antiquated customs from the past and transforming society into a romanticised representation of the past are the objectives (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 243). That is a society built around traditional, severe law and order, family values, and Christianity as the primary religion (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 243). Furthermore, ethnicity and nationalism are intimately associated, according to far-right parties. The goal of far-right parties is to "become more ethnically homogenous to strengthen the nation" (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 242). The country is meant to serve as a symbol of the real people who gave it its founding. The country will not admit anyone who is not one of "the true people." Because they uphold the interests and values of Native Americans at the expense of societal equality, far-right parties are nonegalitarian (Betz, 1994, p. 4). Native Americans' everyday lives should be prioritised; jobs, housing, and healthcare should primarily go to Native Americans and be denied to other ethnic groups (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 245). Such preferences are shared by the country.

Immigration, therefore, poses the greatest challenge to maintaining national identity, security, traditional values, and a homogeneous society. While securing national borders, far-right parties want to limit

immigration into their nation (Rydgren, 2017, p. 486). Immigration will lead to a rise in crime and social unrest. Since immigrants' presence would only make matters worse, far-right parties oppose the social integration of immigrants into society (Betz, 1994, p. 4). Additionally, maintaining distinctive national features requires this. A cultural extinction will result from mixing distinct ethnic groups (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 244). The cultural and ethnic differences are too great to be reconciled (Rydgren, 2007a, p. 244).

In Western European democracies, it has become evident that right-wing populism is on the rise. It appears that far-right-wing parties are gaining an increasing amount of support in national elections. A total of 41 percent of the French votes were cast for Marine Le Pen and the National Rally (NR) during the 2022 presidential election, which took place in France. Here, it's evident that the FN's appeal has grown over the last several years.

Rise of National Rally

Originating in the *Ordre Nouveau* (ON) movement, which was founded in 1969, is *Le Rassemblement National* (Kauffmann, 2016, p. 1). The ON-movement was spearheaded by youthful neo-fascist militants and had its origins in radical revolutionary nationalism (Kauffmann, 2016, p. 3). The ON found it difficult to win over lawmakers and attempted to establish a legitimate party that could actively participate in the electoral political process (Kauffmann, 2016, p. 5). Consequently, in 1972, the *National Front* (NF), also known as the *Front National pour l'unité française*, was founded, with Jean-Marie Le Pen (JMP) serving as its inaugural political leader.

The NF persisted in endorsing the radical far-right ideals of ON. Nonetheless, in contrast to other far-right parties, NF's election campaigns were moderate, according to Kaufmann (2016, p. 1). The political agenda centred on safeguarding the West, figuring out a "third way" between capitalism and communism, and shielding the French from the *Union de la Gauche* and May 68 riot-related crises (Kaufmann, 2016, p. 1, Shields, 2011, p. 80).

NF was marginalised politically and electorally during most of the 1970s. Before the party was officially recognised, NF had difficulty gaining political support (Shields, 2011, p. 82). Shields (2011) stated on

page 82 that NF's goal was to establish itself as a "respectable parliamentary party with broad popular appeal, showing the required deference for the norms of electoral competition in a liberal democracy." As a result, during the 1970s, the NF appeared to deliberately adopt a moderate agenda. For example, NF did not express a strong dislike for immigration. The 1974 election campaign's political platform and JMP's manifesto did not include any mention of immigration policy (Shields, 2011, p. 82).

NF, moreover, took a pro-deeper European integration position. According to NF, who expressed a strong desire for European unification and searched for "limited ways of abandoning sovereignty," France belonged to the same geopolitical entity as Europe as both were parts of the "West" (Davies, 2001, p. 22; Kauffmann, 2016, p. 9). After World War II, the NF was forced to acknowledge the need for stronger European collaboration. It was clear that no party was willing to express a negative opinion about further European integration. Particularly not for a newly formed party such as NF. However, it's possible that NF saw European collaboration as a strategic benefit. A bloc of the European Community might safeguard French identity and values while fending off external threats (Chirinos, 2018, p. 12). NF accepted the trend of greater European integration but did not appear to be pro- or anti-EU. Overall, it appears that NF adhered to far-right ideological principles.

As a result of the economic downturn, a dramatic increase in unemployment, and more vulnerable public opinion, NF started to voice stronger anti-immigrant views during the 1978 parliamentary election campaigns (Shields, 2011, p. 82). According to Shields (2011), p. 82, NF contended that reducing immigration to France was imperative to safeguard national interests, particularly job opportunities for French nationals. In this instance, the party started to take an ethno-nationalistic stance. French nationals were given preference for employment over members of other ethnic groupings. The French public's rights were not equal to those of immigrants, since they were deemed less significant.

In the 1980s, immigration became a focal point of NF policy. Following his triumph in the 1981 presidential contest, Francois Mitterrand and his socialist administration put out a number of pro-immigration proposals (Shields, 2011, p. 84). Nonetheless, popular surveys revealed opposition to these measures (Shields, 2011, p. 84). NF declared its opposition to

the existing elites and condemned the socialist party's pro-immigration policies (Stockemer, 2017, p. 17).

NF instead emphasised the significance of staying below the tolerance threshold, or *seuil de tolerance*. In other words, preserving a balance between French interests like housing, work, schools, social stability, and foreign presence (Shields, 2011, p. 86). Granting legal residency status to a large number of immigrants in France will encourage criminal activity and insecurity. This demonstrates the persistence of ethno-nationalistic discourse that prioritises French speakers above other groups. Only the citizens of the nation may have national interests.

Additionally, it appeared that the NF's rhetoric against immigration was becoming too harsh. NF maintained that integrating immigrants into French society was just not feasible. The cultural and religious features that immigrants bring with them are incompatible with the secular principles of France (Shields, 2011, p. 86). The NF advocated for the return of three million immigrants as the only way to maintain the threshold of tolerance. The broader French national interests were at risk from immigrants, not only their potential for work.

Further European integration also lost favour in the 1980s. The NF started to feel negatively towards the European Community. In order to dissuade the Soviet Union, the US maintained a significant presence and influence throughout Western Europe throughout the Cold War. As a result of its concern over losing control over national sovereignty, NF was concerned about a further level of European integration (Davies, 2001, p. 20). NF received more votes in national and European elections as a result of growing pessimism about socialist rule, unemployment, and anti-immigration sentiments. The NF was able to break away from "its political ghetto" of the 1970s because of an overall improvement in electoral support during the 1980s (Hainsworth, 2004, p. 107).

The NF was able to profit from the immigration debate in the 1990s due to escalating violence in Algeria, terrorist acts, and the danger of radical Islamism. According to a pre-election study conducted in France, 38% of respondents agreed with NF's immigration policies, and JMP was thought to be the most qualified candidate (Shields, 2011, pp. 89–90). The French voters appeared to be more receptive to the NF's patriotic beliefs and anti-immigration stances.

As a result, immigration was consistently promoted by the JMP's election campaigns as a central concern and a major danger to French national interests (Shields, 2011, p. 89). Prior to the 1995 presidential election, JMP promised to give French people priority over foreigners in the areas of employment, social assistance, and education. During his seven-year stint as president, he also advocated the development of four million jobs (Shields, 2011, p. 89). To generate these employment opportunities, JMP persisted in encouraging the return of three million immigrants. The statement on the billboard, "We produce French with the French," implies that only diligent French people are capable of producing French.

The 1992 ratification of the Maastricht Treaty marked a sea change in NF's policies in favour of closer European integration. To regain French border control and national sovereignty, JMP pushed for France's exit from the Schengen Convention and the Maastricht Treaty (Shields, 2011, p. 89).

NF had electoral success (16.86 percent) in the 2002 presidential election. The detoxification process is beginning to show some early symptoms. JMP strategically "softened" the image of the NF party before the 2002 elections by removing the promise to repatriate three million immigrants and reducing the harsh language towards immigration (Shields, 2011, p. 91). During the 2007 presidential campaign, JMP kept up the same tactic. Just two pages out of 68 in NF's 2007 political programme, or around two pages, discussed immigration (Shields, 2011, p. 93). Although it had taken on a more moderate tone, immigration remained a major political issue in North Carolina. The main goals were maintaining national sovereignty and French identity. In the 2007 presidential election, NF received a mere 10.4% of the total votes cast. The easing of immigration laws by the NF did not appear to have a significant impact on voter behaviour. Regarding political advertising, NF persisted in the use of strong language in the 1990s.

Marine Le Pen (MLP) took over as the new head of NF in 2011. Following the 2007 election debacle, MLP made a concerted effort to clean up the party's reputation. The primary objective was to eliminate the outdated NF12 and JMP's antisemitic and xenophobic attitudes (Stockemer & Barisione, 2017, p. 104). MLP changed the political message of the party to actively employ moderate and populist language.

MLP's 2012 presidential platform, "My Project for France and the French People," and "Marine Le Pen, the Voice of the People, the Spirit of France," both overtly display the use of populist language and charismatic leadership (Stockemer & Barisione, 2017, p. 104). MLP portrays herself as a heroic character, a "Jeanne-d'Arc," prepared to save the French people from their predicament. JMP used the populist catchphrase "Le Pen, the people" in the 1980s to further project an image of himself as a charismatic leader. Still, MLP surely withdrew from the severe language of the 1990s, when JMP was recognised for radical messages based on extreme xenophobic and antisemitic remarks (Mayer, 2013, p. 175).

Additionally, MLP has tempered a few of the NF's regulations. MLP, for example, has refrained from speaking harshly or in an excessive manner while discussing immigration. MLP claims that she has nothing against immigration or the assimilation of lawful immigrants. But it is necessary to embrace laicite (secularism) and Christianity (Bastow, 2018, p. 23; Betz, 1994, p. 321). In this instance, MLP asserts that they are against the "Islamization" of France rather than being anti-immigrant (Bastow, 2018, p. 23).

MLP continues to look excessive in contexts like globalisation. MLP persisted in inciting anti-EU sentiment in 2012. She supported France's "exit" from the EU in 2012 and reinstated the French franc (Mayer, 2013, p. 175). There was no discussion of the desire for an EU overhaul. It was vital to secure national independence.

Increased support for NF was shown in the results of the 2017 presidential election. 33.90 percent of the votes went to NF. Internationalisation and Islamic extremism were major campaign issues in the 2017 presidential election (Bastow, 2018, p. 23). MLP suggested a reform of the EU, much as in the 1990s. Specifically, among other reforms, the EU would be reorganised from a supranational to a flexible intergovernmental entity. According to Henley (2017), if the EU failed to implement these measures, a vote inside the EU would be required, as would Frexit. Since the 1990s, there has appeared to be a persistent anti-EU stance that emphasises the need to maintain national autonomy.

A key component of the NF's political programme was combating terrorism and Islamic fundamentalism. MLP pushed for tougher immigration laws by making it impossible for undocumented immigrants

to obtain authorisation to remain in France (Henley, 2017). It would be nearly impossible to become a French citizen. MLP originally adopted the phrase "French first" in reaction to previous terrorist acts. French residents prioritise national concerns, such as social housing and employment, a phenomenon known as ethno-nationalism (Henley, 2017). The immigration policies of the late 1970s, early 1980s, and early 1990s in Newfoundland are comparable to this topic. Since the late 1970s, one of the primary policy concerns has been immigration and employment.

2018 saw MLP drastically rebranded as Rassemblement National (National Rally) instead of Front National (National Front). This stood for a distinct departure from the past as well as the bad connotations connected to the terms JMP and Front National (Startin, 2022, p. 433). Changing the name of the party is a response to a very clear political objective: ending the isolation that the RN experiences by uniting all "patriotic" forces against the "elites," who are represented by the financial sector and liberal globalisation. The Republican Party (LR) and its most conservative voters and elected officials are expected to defect to the RN because they share the party's views on sovereignty, traditional values, and the motto "France to the French." In order to accomplish this, the RN is trying to accelerate the breakup of the traditional conservative right.

Electoral Support for National Rally

Marine Le Pen's party is aiming to take over the government. "Our goal is to gain control of the government," she says, laying out a predicted "victory path" that will begin with the May 2019 European Parliament elections, in which RN finished first with 23.34 percent, continue with the March 2020 City Council elections, the Department of Education and Health Department elections in 2021, and culminate in the spring 2022 presidential election. This conquering plan has the oddity of being implemented with a programme whose essential elements are still the same as those of the pre-Marine Le Pen period but in a new format.

82% of Marine Le Pen's followers thought the fight on terror was "decisive" before the 2017 presidential election; 84% of voters backed the party because they thought it was against illegal immigration; 71% did so because they wanted to see their salaries and purchasing power

increase; and 72% agreed with the party's anti-crime platform. In comparison, just 46% of those who supported Marine Le Pen thought that the public debt crisis was crucial, while 37% expressed interest in environmental concerns and 52% in the state of the educational system (Camus, 2021, p. 92).

Marine Le Pen leads the lower-middle class and working class, receiving 32 percent of employee votes and 37 percent of worker votes, according to an IPSOS-Sterea study released in April 2017 (Camus, 2021, p. 95). The jobless (26 percent) and governmental employees (27 percent) are also its main target audiences. Furthermore, her supporters had the lowest levels of education; 30 percent of them had only completed secondary school, whereas 30 percent of voters with college degrees supported Macron, 24 percent supported Fillon, and 20 percent supported Mélenchon. Age-wise, Marine Le Pen led with 29 percent of voters between the ages of 35 and 49 and earned 27 percent of voters between the ages of 50 and 59. This indicates that her base of support consists of residents who are employed, as opposed to the 18 to 24-year-olds who gave her just 21 percent (she polled 24 percent among those 25 to 34). Last but not least, the older voter is not eager to support Le Pen, who only garnered 19 percent of the vote among those aged 60 to 69, much behind Fillon (27 percent) and Macron (26 percent). The percentage of voters who are over 70 who oppose this idea rises to 49 percent for Fillon, 27 percent for Macron, and only 10 percent for Le Pen. The rationale stems from the baby-boomer and older population's need for stability; they appear to be concerned about potential problems that may arise if the RN were to come to power and are content with Fillon's and Macron's conservative budgetary policies.

Le Pen was chosen by 65 percent of voters in April 2012 because they wanted "change," whereas 59 percent of Francois Fillon's supporters cast their ballots based on his "sound programme." This information comes from an IPSOS poll on the subject. The most startling conclusion of this survey is that Le Pen and Macron appealed to those who desired "change," which was the primary reason for 65 percent of Macron's supporters. Of course, their definitions of change differed greatly: 69 percent of Le Pen's supporters cited immigration as a deciding issue, 46 percent cited terrorism, and 42 percent cited crime (Camus, 2021, p. 100).

NR received 41.45 percent of the vote in the 2022 presidential contest. In the 2022 presidential election, MLP's second-round vote total increased dramatically from 33.9 percent in the 2017 contest to 41.45 percent (Startin, 2022, p. 428). Social and economic concerns served as the foundation for the main NR initiatives. Preserving national sovereignty while quietly challenging immigration and the EU were other characteristics of the NR that were shared with the far right wing party.

Populist rhetoric is still being used in the 2022 electoral campaign. MLP claims that Emmanuel Macron does not speak for "the people." Effective pragmatism: She accuses EM and the present administration of being the corrupt elite, making unfulfilled promises. She criticises EM for ignoring social concerns such as social unfairness, the cost-of-living crisis, economic instability, and excessive petrol costs (Startin, 2022, p. 428). This is a form of social populism, claims Startin (2022, p. 433). MLP provides social relief in direct response to "the people's" concerns.

Intra-Party Competition on Immigration Policy

France's population has increased by 2.3 million over the past 20 years due to immigration, which also brings a greater diversity of origins to the country. In 1975, six nations accounted for 75% of immigration, while in the 2018 census, less than 60% of immigrants were from the top 10 countries of origin (Boubtane, 2022). However, the countries of origin with the strongest links to France are the larger ones: Algeria leads the pack, followed by Morocco, Portugal, Tunisia, and Italy.

Numerous immigration-related policies have been implemented by succeeding administrations, making it challenging to evaluate their individual effects because of the frequency of changes and the fact that many problems stem from uncontrollable circumstances, like the migration crisis in Europe in 2015-16 or the recent Ukrainian mass exodus in millions. Together, though, they show that the government is becoming more interested in more selective immigration laws, which have been implemented with the intention of putting up barriers to discourage highly qualified immigrants and others.

Immigration's impact on the labour market and the far left's political support are more nuanced. While far-left politicians often support refugees, they are typically more hostile to labour migration. For

example, the main far-left party's 2017 candidate, Jean-Luc Mélenchon, questioned France's EU membership, which has permitted a significant amount of low-skilled migration from Eastern Europe. He was in favour of family reunions, amnesty for illegal immigrants, and 10-year residency permits for refugees at the same time. Thus, it is impossible to categorise far-left parties as always in favour of or against immigration. We thus refrain from presenting any testable theories on labour market impacts that might lend credence to far-left candidates. Immigration affects state budgets and policies in addition to the labour market. According to Facchini and Mayda's (2009) research, locals are concerned about the financial impact of migration on the public purse.

The electoral approach employed by the French centre-right from the mid-2000s to the early 2010s was strongly linked to Nicolas Sarkozy's character. In the first round of the 2007 election, Sarkozy's immigration control ideas were intended to offset the FN's potential to split the right-wing support. Sarkozy (2005) stated his goal of raising the proportion of work immigration at the expense of "unwanted inflows" (family reunion and asylum) during a party conference headlined "Selected Immigration, Ensured Immigration." Even though Sarkozy rejected "zero-immigration policies," the FN's election plans were notable for their portrayal of some inflows as undesirable (Carvalho, 2019, p. 371). Consequently, the UMP's stance on immigration restrictions moved into the FN's turf in an attempt to sway the far-right's support for Sarkozy in 2007.

The FN's strategy of portraying immigration as a threat to national identity served as the cornerstone of the party's electoral campaign in the preceding presidential elections, led by Jean Marie Le Pen (FN 2001). The UMP responded by assuming an accommodating stance about the FN's standpoint. The radicalism of the UMP's position on immigration and integration was cemented by a TV appearance in which Sarkozy proposed creating a ministry of immigration and national identity (Carvalho, 2019, p. 371).

The FN, influenced by Le Pen's daughter Marine, moderated its anti-immigrant sentiment in response to the UMP's shift to the right. The head of the FN ran a campaign opposing unchecked immigration, communitarianism's spread, and globalisation. Meanwhile, Segolène Royal, the centre-left candidate for the Parti Socialiste (PS, or Socialist Party), did not pursue an aggressive campaign against the UMP's turn to

the far-right. Royal stressed the value of the national song and the tricolour flag, while Sarkozy suggested establishing a ministry of national identity (Carvalho, 2019, p. 372). Contrary to what was expected, the UMP's accommodating stance towards the FN was successfully strengthened by the intra-party conflicts over immigration and integration in 2007, rather than undermining it as suggested by the research.

Repeating the UMP's 2012 accommodation of the FN did not solve the FN's ownership of their resistance to immigration, prevent Marine from making a strong first-round showing, or stop the one million FN supporters who voted in the first round and shifted in the second round to support the centre-left candidate. Considering the electoral success of the FN in 2012, it seems that the way in which President Sarkozy handled immigration and integration throughout his government, in addition to the political convergence that occurred during the campaign, supported Marine's electoral growth among the French public. Over an extended period, the alignment of the positions of the UMP and the FN regarding these matters encouraged the ideological radicalisation of the voters on the centre-right.

Since 2014, FN has held a majority of the French seats in the European Parliament as well as seats in the Senate. The far-right is currently heavily supported by the military and the police, with around 40% and 70% of the population, respectively. On April 20, 2021, the 60th anniversary of an attempted coup to overthrow Algerian independence, more than a thousand French military personnel—some of whom had connections to the far right—wrote an open letter to President Macron threatening to use force to force him to adopt a tougher stance against "Islamism," an increasingly blatant code for Muslims who are consistently portrayed as France's fifth column (Francois, 2022). When compared to even Macron's ministers, Le Pen's rhetoric about Muslims really seems mild. Marine Le Pen has frequently employed the fascist cliché "halt the 'ensauvagement' [wilding] of society," which is mentioned by Interior Minister Gerald Darmanin (Francois, 2022).

Macron has shown since taking office in May 2017 that he has come a long way from his days as a member of the Socialist Party and the centrist candidate that the election of 2017 portrayed him as. The departure of Macron from the centre was anticipated by historian Robert

Zaretsky. There haven't been many genuine moderate contenders in French political history (Zaretsky, 2017). Islam has been described as a "problem" by almost every wing of the political elite. As the sociologist Hicham Benaissa notes, the more Islam has become a French religion, Naturally, Macron uses more nuance when he refers to Islam as a religion that is in "crisis," or euphemism for "Islamism," and that needs secularism and French laws to rein in its most radical inclinations.

Furthermore, this wave of fascism has no genuine political opposition. Once the adamant adversaries of the far-right, secular leftists have emerged as some of the most outspoken opponents of Muslims' presence in public areas, advocating for ever-broader prohibitions on the headscarf, the "burkini," the building of mosques, and the encouragement of Muslims to act "discreetly" (Francois, 2022). Scholar Jacques Ranciere notes that the left mobilised basic socialist values but distorted them to cater to Le Pen's expanding following in the struggle to defend Republican traditions. There is a clear similarity to Le Pen's national socialism. Many former lefties have since defected to her party, and surveys indicate that around half of left-leaning people no longer support an opposition party (Francois, 2022).

The area in France where one may oppose authoritarian, racist policies is getting smaller everywhere you turn, and far-right ideologies are growing more prevalent. Macron has made an effort to represent the middle ground. However, winning the presidency is not necessary for the far right. Simply put, they must be regarded as the sole credible opposition in a nation where they are already the ones setting the agenda and acting as the political counterbalance.

Conclusion

While Marine Le Pen was unable to win the Élyse Palace in the 2022 presidential election, she did manage to secure 41 percent of the votes in the second round and 1.5 million additional RN votes over the 2017 election, meaning that the outcome might be interpreted as a win for the MLP and N.R. The NR has grown to become the biggest opposition party in the National Assembly from being a marginalised and extreme right-wing party.

In political spheres where the NF once expressed radical opinions, MLP has, on the one hand, adopted a less aggressive approach (directional

philosophy). She sought a more "respectable" immigration and globalisation narrative in the 2000s so as not to come across to French people as being overly radical, hazardous, or careless. In this instance, we can conclude that MLP has attempted to match the intensity of NR to the amount of support for particular policies among the French public.

However, MLP has intensified NR's focus on policies that align with the demands, aspirations, and interests of the French people, a move towards efficient pragmatism. The focus of the NF has switched from the politics of severe immigration to social welfare and economic policies. The NR has gained more traction with a wider segment of French voters by levelling off and intensifying its stance on several political topics. The NR is even more likely to be taken into consideration as a possible ruling party in this situation.

In conclusion, we might contend that the NR has expanded its base of support by cleaning up its party image, tempering its political language, and adjusting to measures that benefit the French people. The NR has evolved from an extremist party with shaky support to a legitimate option along the French left-right political axis, with the ability to form a government. Stated differently, the party has deliberately repositioned itself as a more respectable and moderate organisation to win over more French voters.

References

- Bastow, S. (2018). *The Front national under Marine Le Pen: a mainstream political party?*. French Politics, 16, 19-37. Retrieved from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/s41253-017-0052-7>
- Betz, H. G. (1994). *Radical right-wing populism in Western Europe*. Basingstoke: Macmillan.
- Boubtane, E. (2022). *France Reckons with Immigration Amid Reality of Rising Far Right*. Migration Policy Institute, Retrieved from: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/france-immigration-rising-far-right>
- Camus, Jean-Yves. (2021). The National Rally in 2020: Strengths and Weaknesses of Radical Right in France, in Éva Gedő and Éva Szénási (ed.), *Populism and Migration*, Paris: L'Harmattan.
- Carvalho, J. (2019). Mainstream Party Strategies Towards Extreme Right Parties: The French 2007 and 2012 Presidential Elections. *Government and Opposition*, 54(2), 365–386. doi:10.1017/gov.2017.25

- Chirinos, E. A. (2018). "When in France, do as the French do!": *The Front National and the European Union; A Battle for the Preservation of French Culture. Mapping Politics*, 9. Retrieved from: <file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/1923-7043-2-PB.pdf>
- Davies, P. (2001). *The National Front in France: Ideology, discourse, and power*. London: Routledge. Retrieved from: https://books.google.no/books?hl=en&lr=&id=RDHOCh1y_wQC&oi=fnd&pg=PP11&dq=front+national+rhetoric+1980s+france&ots=j0JqXRNFJ-&sig=WPfoteO5B_5f9cDGJ2xYmgHsSWU&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=front%20national%20rhetoric%201980s%20france&f=false
- Facchini, G., Mayda, A.M. (2009). Does the welfare state affect individual attitudes toward immigrants? Evidence across countries. *Rev. Econ. Stat.* 91 (2), 295–314 . <https://doi.org/10.1162/rest.91.2.295>.
- Francois, M. (2022). *How the Far Right Already Won in France?* Time. Retrieved from: <https://time.com/6170043/french-election-far-right-already-won/>
- Henley, J. (2017). *Marine Le Pen promises liberation from the EU with France-first policies*. The Guardian. Retrieved from: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2017/feb/05/marine-le-pen-promises-liberation-from-the-eu-with-france-first-policies>
- Kauffmann, G. (2016). The origins of the National Front. *Pouvoirs*, 157(2), 5-15. Retrieved from: https://www.cairn-int.info/article-E_POUV_157_0005--the-origins-of-the-national-front.htm
- Mayer, N. (2013). From Jean-Marie to Marine Le Pen: Electoral change on the Far Right. *Parliamentary Affairs*, 66(1), 160-178.
- Rydgren, J. (2007a). *The sociology of the radical right*. *Annu. Rev. Sociol.*, 33, 241-262. Retrieved from: https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/29737762.pdf?refreqid=excelsior%3A7d31499673ff23f6965801096800ae25&ab_segments=&origin=&initiator=&acceptTC=1
- Rydgren, J. (2017). *Radical right-wing parties in Europe: What's populism got to do with it?*. *Journal of language and politics*, 16(4), 485-496. Retrieved from: <https://www.jbe-platform.com/docserver/fulltext/jlp.17024.ryd.pdf?expires=1680958448&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=5211810DD0BA6B944F0DB85F4E5C1F3B>

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- Shields, J. (2011). *Radical or Not So Radical? French Politics, Culture and Society*, 29(3), 78-100. Retrieved from: file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/RADICAL_OR_NOT_SO_RADICAL_Ta.pdf
- Startin, N. (2022). *Marine Le Pen, the Rassemblement National and breaking the 'glass ceiling'? The 2022 French presidential and parliamentary elections. Modern & Contemporary France*, 30(4), 427-443. Retrieved from:
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09639489.2022.2138841>
- Stockemer, D. (2017). *The Front National in France: Continuity and Change Under Jean-Marie Le Pen and Marine Le Pen*. Springer. Retrieved from: file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/FNbook2017.pdf
- Stockemer, D., & Barisione, M. (2017). *The 'new' discourse of the Front National under Marine Le Pen: A slight change with a big impact. European Journal of Communication (London)*, 32(2), 100-115. Retrieved from:
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/epub/10.1177/0267323116680132>
- Zaretsky, R. (2017). "The Radical Centrism of Emmanuel Macron," *Foreign Policy* (blog), accessed February 26, 2024, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2017/04/24/the-radical-centrism-of-emmanuel-macron/>
- Zaslove, A. (2008). *Exclusion, Community, and a Populist Political Economy: The Radical Right as an Anti-Globalization Movement. Comparative European Politics (Houndmills, Basingstoke, England)*, 6(2), 169-189. Retrieved from:
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/palgrave.cep.6110126>